

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCER ON BRAND ATTITUDE AND PURCHASE INTENTION: INCOME LEVEL AND AGE AS MODERATING VARIABLE IN HEALTHY FOOD INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of credibility, trust, behavioral control, subjective norms, expertise, conformity to attitudes on influencers. In addition, the effect of attitudes towards influencers and attitudes towards brands on buying interest is also investigated. The study findings show that perceived credibility and trust have a positive effect on attitudes towards influencers. However, perceived behavioral control does not make a positive contribution to this attitude. Subjective Norms and Perceived Expertise play a positive role in shaping attitudes towards influencers. Likewise, Perceived Congruence affects the increase in attitudes towards influencers. This study also reveals a significant positive correlation between attitude toward influencers and attitudes toward brands, both of which influence purchase intention. Income level does not moderate the relationship between attitude toward influencers and purchase intention, but moderates the relationship between attitude toward brand and purchase intention. whereas age does not moderate the relationship between attitude toward influencer and attitude toward brand towards purchase intention.

Keywords: Perceived Credibility, Trust, Perceived Behavior Control, Subjective Norms, Perceived Expertise, Perceived Congruence, Attitude Toward The Influencer, Attitude Toward The Brand, Purchase Intention.

INTRODUCTION

Human understanding of the importance of health trends has experienced a significant increase in recent years (Citra, et. al, 2023). The increase in health awareness is reported by the Global Health Security Index (GHSI) in 2021, the average global health score reaches 38.9 points on a 100 point scale. This global health security index study involved 195 countries and measured performance in six categories, namely prevention, detection and reporting, speed of response, health systems, compliance with international standards, and environmental risk (Global Health Security Index, 2021). This has led to the increasing popularity of healthy food as well as a healthy diet which has resulted in an increase in Indonesian people's interest in healthy food.

Information about this healthy diet can be obtained by writing on the internet or various social media timelines, where many diet influencers are currently discussing how to diet properly and correctly (Fajriani, Nugrahani, & Dirgantara, 2021). Many companies try to win the competition by taking advantage of existing business opportunities and trying to implement the right marketing strategy to dominate the market (Iskamto, 2020). Nowadays people can easily find information about lifestyles and healthy diets, especially since diet and fitness influencers share tips and ways to diet well and have fun (Luthfiyyah, Setiyanti, & Dida, 2020). With the increasingly advanced development of the internet, social media is also experiencing rapid growth.

Purchase intention or purchase intention refers to the possibility that a consumer plans or is willing to buy a particular brand in the future (Harpe et.al, 2015). Theory of Planned Behavior says that an increase in intention reflects an increase in the opportunity to carry out the behavior. In the context of influencer marketing, previous studies have indicated that consumers' attitudes toward certain brands directly influence their purchase intentions (Pradhana et al., 2016). Influencer marketing strategies can affect attitudes towards influencers, attitudes towards brands, and purchase intentions owned by consumers (Immanuel & Bianda, 2021).

One of the influencers who shared her diet journey was Clarissa Putri. Clarissa Putri started her career as a celebgram and big size Indonesian fashion model, known for actively sharing content about beauty, makeup and fashion on social media (Putri, 2022). Clarissa Putri consistently follows a healthy diet, and she shares her struggles with her diet on her Instagram account. In one of his uploads, he shows the process of dieting, exercising, and losing weight gradually. The video has been watched 4.3 million times and has 3,326 comments with 196 thousand likes. (Ekrep, 2022). Based on the video titled recap diet 2021 and Clarissa's thanks to those who support her, one of them is the Yellow Fit Kitchen,

Based on this, a marketer needs to identify appropriate influencers to promote their product advertisements. Therefore, influencers are needed who have strong persuasive abilities to influence their followers (Prasetio, Alkausar, & Hardjanti, 2023). The ability of an influencer can be observed through the consumer's response to it. Consumer responses to an influencer have been shown to be directly influenced by the influencer's perceived credibility, trust, perceived expertise, and perceived congruence (Nisa & Kristaung, 2022).

According to Ajzen (2011), purchase intention has been shown to be influenced by consumer attitudes according to the theory of planned behavior. This theory states that attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control affect individual intentions to perform certain behaviors. In the theory of planned behavior, intention is considered as a direct result of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. The success of influencers as brand carriers can be ensured through the positive relationship between different characteristics of influencers and consumer purchase intentions (Saima & Khan, 2020).

According to research by Jin (2018), having a positive view of celebrities who are easy to recognize can result in a more positive attitude towards the brand. According to Chetioui et al. (2020), in the context of the relationship between attitudes and consumer purchase intentions, consistency is generally higher when the consumer is actively involved. Therefore, it is important to choose influencers carefully, because a liked influencer will create a positive view of the brand and increase purchase intention.

Purchase intention itself can be influenced by various factors, one of which is personal factors such as demography, these demographic factors such as age, gender, income, education, and others (Khairullah, 2020). Hernández et al., (2011) discussing online buying behavior shows that higher income makes users feel the implicit risk in making online purchases is lower. However, low incomes may discourage users from making online purchases as they fear financial loss if their decisions are not successful.

Age is also considered to be a factor that can influence purchase intention, this is because younger individuals tend to be more responsive and have greater experience with the internet, so factors such as usability and attitude become more important to them (Tiruwa et.al, 2018). Additionally, older users lack experience with Internet media, which makes it difficult for them to evaluate the benefits offered in the context of receiving information online, for example, from influencers (Trocchia & Janda, 2000).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Perceived Credibility

Credibility is the level of consumer trust in the sources of information that are conveyed to them (Sugianto, 2022). Someone who is seen as trustworthy and has an understanding of certain issues, such as brand reliability, is able to convince others to take action (Wijaya & Saryadi, 2015). Meanwhile, the influence of fashion influencers on consumers illustrates that perceived credibility is a belief or reputation which is an important factor in selecting and following an influencer (Chetioui, et. al, 2020).

Trusts

Trust is when a person is willing to establish a relationship with another party based on the belief that the trusted party will fulfill their obligations properly and as expected. Trust is easier to develop between individuals who have the same interests and goals, so it is easier to change individual beliefs than the beliefs of a group (Ainurrofiq, 2017).

Consumer trust in an influencer can increase the tendency of consumers to trust the recommendations of the influencer. Thus, influencers who have a trustworthy reputation have a greater opportunity to influence consumer attitudes, choices, and purchase intentions (Chetioui, et. al, 2020).

Perceived Behavioral Control

Perceived Behavioral Control, also known as behavioral control, is a person's feelings about the level of ease or difficulty in carrying out a particular behavior (Ajzen, 2005). The higher the perception of behavioral control, the stronger a person's intention to carry out the behavior under consideration (Tiranti, 2020).

Perception of perceived behavioral control can be influenced by information provided by someone about a behavior, observations of people's experiences related to that behavior, as well as other factors that can influence perceptions regarding the level of ease or difficulty in carrying out certain behaviors (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

Subjective Norms

Subjective norms refer to a person's perception of social pressure to perform or not perform a behavior (Ajzen, 1988). Subjective norms are part of influencer marketing that measures the extent to which a person is willing to follow the opinions of others in his behavior (Chopra et. al, 2021).

In the context of social media, audiences as consumers use brand information messages obtained from influencers as a subjective guide to determine their purchase intentions (Chetioui et al., 2020).

Perceived Expertise

Expertise refers to knowledge, experience, or skills that are felt to be owned by sources related to the topic to be conveyed (Lukito, 2018). When viewed as a dimension of influencer, Perceived behavioral control is the influencer's expertise refers to the level of knowledge, experience, or competence they have, which can provide more effective persuasion to the audience as target consumers (Chopra et al., 2021). Consumer perceptions of influencer expertise that are considered experts can provide a more accurate and valid assessment of a product. To measure the expertise of an influencer, the indicators used include factors of professionalism, experience, broad knowledge, adequate qualifications, and skilled expertise (Chetioui et al., 2020).

Perceived Congruence

Congruence can be explained as the extent to which the endorser and the endorsed brand or product have harmony or suitability. This congruence focuses on the attributes and characteristics that are aligned between the endorser and the product or brand (Lukito, 2018). It is often found that the higher the level of conformity between the supporting image and the product or brand, the higher the response or attitude response towards the brand and influencer (Mathys et al., 2016). Perceived congruence relates to the extent to which the influencer is similar or compatible with the audience in terms of behavior, personality or self-image. The greater the perceived level of similarity or suitability between influencers and consumers.

Attitude toward Influencers

Attitude is a learned tendency to behave consistently which can provide benefits or harm to an object (Schiffman & Wisenblit, 2019). So that attitude toward influencers can be considered as an assessment that indicates whether a person likes or dislikes the people involved in a particular event. When consumers have reasons they think are good for following the attitude exemplified by an influencer, consumers' willingness to follow them will increase (Chetioui et al., 2020). In this case Social Media Influencers are used as examples of role models or role models who show leadership in tastes and opinions.

Attitude toward Brands

Attitude toward Brand is a personal evaluation of likes or dislikes, emotional feelings, and behavioral tendencies that are maintained by an individual (Kotler Philip and Gary Armstrong., 2009). Attitude towards the brand refers to the direction of consumer perception and brand strength. With a deep understanding of brand attitudes, marketers can find out customers' views of brands and understand their purchase intentions (Yoon & Park, 2012).

Purchase Intentions

Interest is a fixed tendency to pay attention to certain things and remember them. When someone is interested in something, they always pay attention to it and feel good about it. Therefore, it differs from attention in that interest is always followed by a feeling of pleasure, which results in satisfaction, whereas attention is brief or absent for a long time (Harpe et.al, 2015). Each individual's buying interest is always hidden, and no one can predict what consumers want or expect (Kusnawan et al., 2019).

Hypothesis

Research conducted by Nam & Dan (2018) explains that perceived credibility is an important factor in considering following an influencer. In this context, the credibility seen from an influencer has a crucial role in shaping the attitude that is accepted by his followers. Another study by Lagner and Eiseng (2011) confirms that, although attractiveness can have an immediate impact, the credibility trusted by an influencer will have a more lasting influence on consumer behavior towards a brand. Based on this description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H1: Perceived credibility has a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

According to research by Jin et al. (2019), trust is a key factor that makes Instagram influencers have a big influence on consumer attitudes. So that in order for the advertisements to be effective, an influencer needs to gain the trust of his consumers (Schouten, et.al, 2020). Research conducted by Chetioui et.al (2020) says that there is a positive influence between trust and attitudes towards influencers. Based on this description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H2: Trust has a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

There is research showing that perceptions of behavior control are positively related to a person's intentions, because behavioral control is based on beliefs that are formed through previous experience regarding this behavior (Wiryanto, et. al, 2018). Research conducted by Putra et. al (2016) explained that the stronger the Perceived behavioral control, the higher the possibility for someone to buy a product. Based on these explanations, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H3: Perceived behavioral control has a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

There is research which explains that there is a relationship between subjective norms and purchase intentions and attitudes towards influencers depending on the role of subjective norms as individual beliefs about other people's opinions, which affect individual intentions to do or not do something, including how the audience perceives their trust in certain influencers (Lim et al., 2017). Research conducted by Chetioui et al. (2020) also show a positive relationship between subjective norms and customer attitudes towards influencers. Based on the aforementioned information, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H4: Subjective norms have a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

Research conducted by Chopra et. al (2021) results that the level of knowledge, experience, or competence possessed by influencers is able to provide more effective persuasion to the audience as target consumers. Previous research by Bergkvist et al. (2016) explained that individuals who have high expertise can influence consumer views because they are more likely to make accurate and valid judgments.

Research from Chetioui et.al (2020) also confirms that perceived expertise or expertise is another important factor that plays a role in shaping attitudes towards influencers.

Based on the aforementioned information, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H5: Perceived expertise has a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

Research conducted by Rohman (2017) explains that the suitability or compatibility between the performance of products or services offered by companies and influencers can influence consumer intentions as part of their attitudes.

Xu and Prat (2018) stated that consumers tend to follow an influencer when they have similarities in personality traits, lifestyle, or preferences.

Research conducted by Chetioui et al. (2020) also revealed a positive relationship between perceived congruence and attitudes toward influencers. Based on this description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H6: Perceived congruence has a positive effect on attitude toward social media influencers.

Research conducted by Chetioui et al. (2020) explained that attitudes towards influencers can positively influence attitudes towards brands and also affect one's purchase intention. Based on further research by Bergkvist et al. (2016) stated that attitudes toward influencers can act as direct drivers influencing purchase intentions.

Pranamawati & Astuti (2017) in their research stated that Attitude toward influencers is one of the elements in forming a brand impression. Based on this description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H7: Attitude toward social media influencers has a positive effect on attitude toward the brand.

H8: Attitude toward social media influencers has a positive effect on purchase intention.

Research conducted by Kim (2016) states that a positive brand attitude will have an impact on consumer purchase intentions. The better the consumer's attitude towards the product, the higher the consumer's purchase intention (Astutik, 2019).

Research conducted by Chetioui et al. (2020) confirms that attitudes towards brands can affect buying interest. Based on the description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H9: Attitude toward the brand has a positive effect on purchase intention on the brand.

Research on online buying behavior shows that higher income leads users to perceive lower implicit risk in making online purchases.

However, low incomes can discourage users from making online purchases because they are worried that they will incur financial losses if their decisions are not successful (Hernández et al., 2011). Research conducted by Dewi et.al, (2015) explains that income level has a positive effect on purchase intention.

This statement is also supported by Mahendra & Ardani's research (2015) which states the same thing. Based on this description, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H10: Attitude toward social media influencers has a positive effect on purchase intention with income level as a moderator

H11: Attitude toward the brand has a positive effect on purchase intention with income level as a moderator

Mahendra & Ardani (2015) explained that age can positively influence a person's purchase intention. Research suggests that younger individuals tend to be more responsive and have greater experience with the internet, so factors such as usability and attitude become more important to them. Several previous studies have also addressed the lack of experience of older users with Internet media, which makes it difficult for them to evaluate the benefits offered in the context of online shopping (Trocchia and Janda, 2000). Sawaftah et. al (2020) and Tiruwa et. al (2018) has conducted research that uses age as a moderator of buying interest, but the two studies have obtained different results. Based on the description above, the author formulates the hypothesis as follows:

H12: Attitude toward social media influencers has a positive effect on purchase intention with age as a moderator.

H13: Attitude toward the brand has a positive effect on purchase intention with age as a moderator.

Referring to the results of previous research and the hypotheses that have been developed, then a research model is created as depicted in the following.

Figure 1: Framework

Source: Developed for this research (2023)

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Object and Analytic Unit

The population is all groups of people, events, or objects that researchers think are interesting to study and will serve as the boundaries of the research results obtained (Indrawati, 2015). This means that the research will only be applied to the selected population. The population of this study are followers of Clarissa Putri influencers.

The sample is defined as a subset of the population consisting of several members strategically selected from the population (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). The number of samples used in this study was determined using a non-probability sampling technique. According to (Indrawati, 2015), non-probability sampling is a technique in which members of the population do not have the same opportunity to be selected as a sample, and it is not known whether they have the same or different opportunities. The sampling method refers to Bachrudin & Tobing (2003) which determines the number of samples based on the number of variables used in the study. So that the research sample was set as many as 200 respondents. This is because the number of variables used in this study are 11 variables. The 200 respondents in this study have the criteria of being followers of Clarissa Putri's social media and have an interest in buying healthy food products from Yellow Fit Kitchen.

Analysis Technique and Model Testing

This study uses a quantitative research approach and uses an online survey as a data collection method. The data analysis technique chosen is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), which is widely known and used to build and evaluate statistical models that describe causal relationships.

SEM is a statistical method used to check and validate the model. When researchers have many variables with several indicators, and these variables can be distinguished into exogenous and endogenous variables, then SEM is most suitable to be used (Hair et al., 2010).

In this study, the SmartPLS software is used because it is considered robust because it does not depend on various assumptions, requires a relatively small sample size, including bootstrap,

In testing the SEM-PLS there are two main stages, namely the evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model) and the evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model). The Outer Model is used to assess the validity and reliability of measurements, while the Inner Model is used to determine the value of Goodness of Fit and R-square.

Validity test indicates the extent to which a measuring instrument can measure what is to be measured. Therefore, the higher the validity of a measuring instrument, the more accurate the target and the more it reflects what should be measured (Indrawati, 2015).

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is usually used to evaluate convergent validity, which measures how much variance in an indicator can be explained by latent variables (Hair et al., 2017). AVE was tested through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The conditions that must be met are $AVE > 0.5$, and if the AVE value exceeds 0.5 it means that the indicator can converge and represent a variable.

The reliability test is related to the level of trust, dependability, consistency, and stability of measurement results. Reliability test aims to test the consistency of each indicator in a measuring instrument. Reliability testing can be done by measuring Construct Reliability (CR). If and Construct Reliability (CR) ≥ 0.7 , it can be concluded that the indicators are consistent.

Testing the entire model can be explained by the Goodness of Fit or the level of suitability and the significance of the structural model coefficients. Goodness of Fit indicates how well the model fits a set of observations. If the GOF value shows a slight difference between the observed covariance and the estimated covariance matrix, it is considered good (Hair et al., 2010). The fit index criterion in SmartPLS is Chi-Square (χ^2), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual or SRMR, RMS Theta, and Normed Fit Index (NFI) (Ghozali, 2021).

In assessing the structural model, we begin by examining the R-square value for each endogenous variable as an indicator of the predictive power of the structural model. Changes in the value of R-square (R²) can be used to explain the substantive effect of specific exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables. The R-square values are 0.67, 0.33 and 0.19 respectively, it can be concluded that they represent strong, medium and weak models (Ghozali, 2021).

Hypotheses in research need to be tested to prove the relationship between variables in a research model (Indrawati, 2015). In this study used a one-way hypothesis test. One-sided testing involves a rejection area for H₀ only on one side, both on the right and left sides (Indrawati, 2015). Since there is only one rejection region, the size of this region is equal to the significance level (α), and the critical value is usually denoted by Z α . If $\alpha = 0.05$, if the t-statistic or research t value is greater than 1.65, then H₀ is rejected. Conversely, if the t-statistic or research t value ≤ 1.65 , then H₀ is accepted.

RESULTS

Questionnaires were distributed using the Google Form to Clarisa Putri's social media followers and who had an interest in Yellow Fit Kitchen's healthy food. After distributing the questionnaire, 237 respondents were obtained, with 37 respondents not meeting the criteria in the screening questions because they did not follow Clarissa Putri's social media accounts or did not have an interest in Yellow Fit Kitchen products. Therefore, this study only got 200 respondents. It was found that 73% or 146 of the respondents were female, and 27% or 54 of the respondents were male. The average age of respondents who are followers of Clarissa Putri's social media and have an interest in Yellow Fit kitchen products ranges from 20 to 26 years. Furthermore.

Measurement (Outer) Model

The results of the study used PLS-SEM measurements using the SmartPLS 3.2.9 software. The outer model aims to define constructs or variables (Hair et al., 2010). Testing the validity and reliability assessment can be done by evaluating the measurement of the outer model. Validity testing is measured through the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, while reliability testing is measured through the Composite Reliability value.

Table 1: Validity Testing

Variable	AVE (>0.5)	Information
Perceived Credibility	0.677	Valid
Trusts	0.670	Valid
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.741	Valid
Subjective Norms	0.728	Valid
Perceived Expertise	0.722	Valid
Perceived Congruence	0.705	Valid
Income Level	1,000	Valid
age	1,000	Valid
Attitude toward Influencers	0.594	Valid
Attitude toward Brands	0.667	Valid
Purchase Intentions	0.781	Valid

Source: Results of data processing (2023)

The table above shows that each indicator has a value > 0.50 which indicates a strong correlation between each indicator and each variable. It can be seen that all variables have an AVE value of greater than 0.50, this shows that the indicators in a variable can be integrated and represent each variable itself, thus indicating its validity.

Table 2: Reliability Testing

Variable	Composite Reliability (>0.6)	Information
Perceived Credibility	0.863	Reliable
Trusts	0.859	Reliable
Perceived Behavioral Control	0.851	Reliable
Subjective Norms	0.843	Reliable
Perceived Expertise	0.886	Reliable
Perceived Congruence	0.877	Reliable
Income Level	1,000	Reliable
age	1,000	Reliable
Attitude toward Influencers	0.854	Reliable
Attitude toward Brands	0.909	Reliable
Purchase Intentions	0.877	Reliable

Source: Results of data processing (2023)

Based on table 2 it can be seen that each indication of the variable has a strong consistency and trust value because the total value of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability variables has a value of > 0.70. After testing the validity and reliability, it is evident that all indicators and variables in this study are valid and reliable.

Structural (Inner) Models

Fit models

The results of the fit model show that Chi-Square (χ^2) of 1089.573 is considered good because it has a value of <3 times the degree of freedom, df in this study itself has a value of 1.371. Standardized Root Mean Residual (SRMR) of 0.061 is considered good because the value is <0.1. Then RMS Theta has a value of 0.163 which means it is not good because it is > 0.12. In addition, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) of 0.721 is good because the value is between 0.00 – 1.00. That is, this research model is an appropriate research model and is feasible to use.

R Square

The R Square test is carried out to measure the extent to which variations in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables, and to find out how much influence the independent variables have on the dependent (endogenous) variable. The higher the R Square value, the greater the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable.

The highest R Square test results were found in the attitude toward influencer variable with a value of 0.843. This means that the attitude toward influencer variable can be explained by 84.3% of the variables perceived credibility, trust, perceived behavioral control, subjective norms, perceived expertise, and perceived congruence, while the remaining 15.7% is explained by other factors not examined. The R Square value for the attitude toward brand variable is 0.678, which means that brand image can be explained by 67.8% by the attitude toward influencer variable, and the remaining 32.2% is explained by other factors not examined. the purchase intention variable has an R Square of 0.680, which means that 68% of purchase intention can be explained by the variables income, age, attitude toward influencer.

Hypothesis Testing

Following an examination of the previous discussion of the external and internal models, hypothesis and significance testing was performed. To assess each interrelationship between variables based on the hypotheses that have been previously set, hypothesis testing is carried out. The t-value, p-value, and path coefficient are used in hypothesis testing. The following lists the findings of significance and hypothesis testing:

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Value	Results
H1	0.210	3,048	0.001	Accepted
H2	0.226	2,501	0.006	Accepted
H3	0.001	0.020	0.492	Rejected
H4	0.135	2,805	0.003	Accepted
H5	0.253	3,921	0.000	Accepted
H6	0.218	2,688	0.004	Accepted
H7	0.824	22,847	0.000	Accepted
H8	0.308	2,844	0.002	Accepted
H9	0.529	4,957	0.000	Accepted
H10	-0.195	1,759	0.040	Rejected
H11	0.200	2,174	0.015	Accepted
H12	0.081	0.661	0.254	Rejected
H13	-0.041	0.338	0.368	Rejected

Source: Results of data processing (2023)

- 1) Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that the relationship between perceived credibility and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 3.048 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.001 with a value of < 0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between perceived credibility on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The amount of influence exerted by perceived credibility on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.210, which means it has an

effect of 21%. This indicates that credibility has a role in how consumers view influencers.

- 2) Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that the relationship between Trust and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 2.501 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.006 with a value of < 0.05 . That is, there is a positive and significant influence between trust and attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The amount of influence given by trust on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.226, which means it has an effect of 22.6%. This indicates that consumer trust in influencers can influence consumer attitudes towards influencers.
- 3) Based on the results of the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between perceived behavioral control and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 0.020 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.492 with a value of < 0.05 . That is, there is no positive and significant influence between perceived behavioral control on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be accepted and H_1 is rejected. The magnitude of the influence exerted by perceived behavioral control on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.001, meaning that it only has an effect of 0.1%. This indicates that in this study,
- 4) Based on the results of the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between subjective norms and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 2.805 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.003 with a value of < 0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between subjective norms on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The magnitude of the influence given by subjective norms on the attitude toward social media influencers of Clarissa Putri can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.135, which means it has an effect of 13.5%. This indicates an individual's desire to please other people who have internal control can influence their attitude towards influencers.
- 5) Based on the results of the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between perceived expertise and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 2.688 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.000 with a value of < 0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between perceived expertise on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The amount of influence given by perceived expertise on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.253, which means it has an effect of 25.3%. This indicates that the higher the consumer evaluates the expertise of the influencer, the more positive the consumer's assessment of the influencer will be.
- 6) Based on the results of hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between perceived congruence and attitude toward social media influencers Clarissa Putri has a t statistic of 2.501 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of

0.004 with a value of <0.05 . That is, there is a positive and significant influence between perceived congruence on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The magnitude of the influence exerted by perceived congruence on attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri can be identified through the path coefficient value, which is 0.218, which means it has an effect of 21.8%.

- 7) Based on the results of the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri and attitude toward the brand at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand has a t statistic of 22.847 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.000 with a value of <0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri on attitude toward the brand at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The magnitude of the influence exerted by the attitude toward social media influencer Clarissa Putri on attitude toward the brand at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand can be identified through the path coefficient value, which is 0.824, which means it has an effect of 82.4%.
- 8) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward influencer Clarissa Putri and purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand has a t statistic of 2.844 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.002 with a value of <0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between attitude toward influencer Clarissa Putri on purchase intention for the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The amount of influence exerted by Clarissa Putri's attitude toward influencer on purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand can be identified through the path coefficient value, which is 0.308, which means it has an effect of 30.8%.
- 9) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward the brand and purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand has a t statistic of 4.957 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.000 with a value of <0.05 . This means that there is a positive and significant influence between attitude toward the brand and purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand, so that H_0 can be rejected and H_1 accepted. The magnitude of the influence exerted between the attitude toward the brand on purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand can be identified through the path coefficient value, which is 0.529, which means it has an effect of 52.9%. This indicates that the attitude towards the brand begins with a cognitive process that stimulates and influences consumer intentions to buy the products offered.
- 10) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between Clarissa Putri's attitude toward influencer and purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by income level has a t statistic of 1.759 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.040 with a value of <0.05 . That is, there is no positive and significant influence between attitude toward influencer Clarissa Putri on purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by income level, so that H_0 can be accepted and H_1 is rejected. The amount of influence exerted by Clarissa Putri's attitude toward influencer on purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by income level can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is -0.195 meaning it has a negative value.

- 11) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward the brand and purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand, which is moderated by income level, has a t statistic of 2.174 with a value of > 1.65 , and a p value of 0.015 with a value of < 0.05 . That is, there is a positive and significant influence between attitude toward the brand on purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by the income level, so that H0 can be rejected and H1 accepted. The magnitude of the influence exerted between the attitude toward the brand on purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand, which is moderated by the income level, can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.200, which means it has an effect of 20%.
- 12) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward influencer Clarissa Putri and purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by age has a t statistic of 0.661 with a value of < 1.65 , and a p-value of 0.254 with a value of > 0.05 . That is, there is no positive and significant influence between attitude toward influencer Clarissa Putri on purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by age, so that H0 can be accepted and H1 is rejected. The amount of influence exerted by Clarissa Putri's attitude toward influencer on purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by age can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is 0.081, meaning that it only has an effect of 8.1%. Other environmental factors in demographic composition such as age can lead to trends in consumer behavior, thus allowing for a shift in trend because social media is dominated by millennial segmentation.
- 13) Based on the hypothesis testing conducted, it shows that the relationship between attitude toward the brand and purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by age has a t statistic of 0.338 with a value of < 1.65 , and a p value of 0.368 with a value of > 0.05 . That is, there is no positive and significant influence between attitude toward the brand on purchase intention at the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand which is moderated by age, so that H0 can be accepted and H1 is rejected. The magnitude of the influence exerted between the attitude toward the brand on purchase intention on the Yellow Fit Kitchen brand moderated by Age can be seen through the path coefficient value, which is -0.041, which means it has no effect.

CONCLUSION

Marketing through social media using influencers is nothing new nowadays. Even so, there is still a need for effective understanding and development by marketers. The use of influencers in promoting products or brands can increase a positive view of the brand and also increase buying interest. This view of influencers has a huge influence in giving a positive attitude towards the brand. This means that a good influencer will increase good views of the brand.

Seeing this, marketers must be able to identify influencers properly and carefully select influencers to choose from. Factors of perceived credibility, trust, subjective norms, perceived expertise, and perceived congruence can be used as a basis for marketers to choose influencers because they have an influence in increasing positive views on influencers. The factor with the greatest influence is perceived expertise. This means that consumers tend to prefer to follow content and recommendations submitted by

influencers who are considered experts in their fields. To overcome some of the identified limitations, this study presents some recommendations for future research:

- 1) The environmental factors chosen to moderate the relationship between variables are not entirely influential. Therefore, further researchers can look for additional variables to investigate attitudes toward influencers, attitudes toward brands and purchase intentions
- 2) This study only used 200 samples with respondents with a young tendency and incomes that were still not high, so that future researchers could increase the number of participants to increase the generalization of the findings.

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